

STUDY OF THE PROCESSING PARAMETERS OF SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES BY SQUEEZE CASTING

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ABSTRACT

The influence of the processing parameters in the fabrication of A356 / Al₂O₃ MMCs by the squeeze casting process has been studied following a two level factorial design. The experiments were carried out according to the cited design, and compared by testing their tensile strength. The evaluation of the strength data revealed that low fibre volume fraction, moderate die and metal temperature, high pressure and high preform temperature gave the best results. Based on these results, it is recommended to extend the study using an Anova or a lineal model design in order to obtain the control equation of the process.

Keywords: Squeeze Casting, Aluminium Matrix, Manufacturing, Optimisation, Experimental design technique.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) have a promising future in coming years because of their excellent specific properties as well as performance-price ratio. Light metals like aluminium, magnesium and copper can advantageously be substituted by MMCs in a great variety of potential applications, such as automotive, electrical, electronic, defence and aerospace industries (1).

Many different techniques can be employed to produce MMC materials, being of particular interest the Squeeze Casting technique (often known as liquid metal forging). In this process a preheated fibre preform is located in a mould where it is infiltrated by molten metal and then rapidly solidified. It is the most widely studied and employed method for producing aluminium matrix composites reinforced with carbon, alumina and other fibres (2). Because of its short turn-around time, good microstructural control and final near net shapes obtained, it is particularly suitable for large scale industrial production of MMC products (3).

Several processing parameters have a direct and strong influence on the final properties of the product. Therefore, the obtention of an outstanding MMC requires the optimisation of the processing parameters, being the subject of the present paper. An experimental design technique has been applied in order to get the maximum information and obtain the process parameters yielding the best performance product with a reasonable effort.

Among the different experimental designs, Anova and Multiple Regression (4) analysis have been employed because they allow the definition of the optimum process levels and the development of the equation that rules the process. This type of analysis also takes into account possible interactions

between different variables, fact that other techniques like Taguchi do not do. Other reason for the choice of this technique is the interest in optimising the process and not the cost related functions.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The materials employed for the production of the MMCs are A356 aluminium alloy and Saffil δ -alumina short fibres produced by ICI (Imperial Chemical Industries) trademark. The fibres are supplied by Vernaware in preformed discs 20mm thick and 100mm diameter, containing 10-20% volume fibres.

The Squeeze Casting technique involves the infiltration of the metal inside the preform under pressure: The fibre preform is preheated in an oven and then is placed inside a mould which is preheated too. The liquid metal is then poured in the mould and the pressure is applied forcing the metal into the preform and promoting solidification to occur in a short time due to the large heat transfer.

The experiments were designed according to the following variables: Fibre volume fraction, infiltration temperatures of the metal, of the preform, and of the mould-die, and the infiltration pressure. An orthonormal array was prepared between the values gathered in Table I, which were subsequently coded into +1/-1 values forming a half factorial fraction 2^{5-1} shown in table II:

Vf: Fibre volume fraction	Range: 10 - 20%	Coded: +1 -1
Tu: Mold and Die temperature	Range: 250° - 350°	Coded: +1 -1
Tm: Temperature of the metal	Range: 700° - 750°	Coded: +1 -1
Tp: Preform temperature	Range: 500° - 700°	Coded: +1 -1
Pr: Infiltration Pressure	Range: 10-50 MPa	Coded: +1 -1

Exp. Run	Vf	Tm	Tp	Tu	Pr	Exp. Run	Vf	Tm	Tp	Tu	Pr
1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	9	-1	-1	-1	+1	+1
2	+1	-1	-1	-1	-1	10	+1	-1	-1	+1	+1
3	-1	+1	-1	-1	+1	11	-1	+1	-1	+1	-1
4	+1	+1	-1	-1	+1	12	+1	+1	-1	+1	-1
5	-1	-1	+1	-1	+1	13	-1	-1	+1	+1	-1
6	+1	-1	+1	-1	+1	14	+1	-1	+1	+1	-1
7	-1	+1	+1	-1	-1	15	-1	+1	+1	+1	+1
8	+1	+1	+1	-1	-1	16	+1	+1	+1	+1	+1

Table I
Squeeze casting conditions

Table II
Experiments design

This array is built using the Yates design (5), where the principal factors are confused with higher level interactions. It gives IV grade resolution and, therefore, 2nd order interactions can be confused. The factor P_r can also be confused with the triple interaction T_m*T_p*T_u.

The response selected for the evaluation of the results is the *Tensile strength*. The tensile tests were performed according to ASTM D 3552-77 using cylindrical threaded specimens of 50,8 mm total length. Six tensile specimens were taken from each sample according to figure 1, studying in this way the variability of the response in each sample. Fracture surfaces were examined by S.E.M. in order to know the influence of microstructure in the mechanical behaviour of the materials.

Figure 1.
Scheme of the Composite showing the place where tensile specimens were taken

The infiltration were performed following the order of the design (Table II), while the sequence of the tensile tests was randomised to avoid systematic errors. The final order of the tests was:

8 - 4 - 15 - 16 - 13 - 2 - 6 - 9 - 3 - 10 - 12 - 11 - 1 - 5 - 14 - 7

3- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained in the tensile tests are gathered in table III:

Exp. Run	Specimen		Tensile c	Strength (MPa)		
	a	b		d	e	f
1	169,0	167,9	b.s.	179,2	137,8	138,8
2	159,6	155,2	b.s.	146,5	149,5	110,7
3	166,9	126,8	11,90	133,3	141,5	140,6
4	107,8	112,2	111,6	116,6	106,7	117,2
5	184,7	190,0	148,2	174,8	188,9	190,1
6	131,8	164,6	138,8	176,1	133,5	180,1
7	b.s.	b.s.	b.s.	124,1	112,0	99,40
8	95,80	97,50	101,5	b.s.	114,6	b.s.
9	b.s.	148,4	129,6	133,3	129,9	129,8
10	b.s.	147,5	135,0	137,0	136,8	110,5
11	b.s.	b.s.	b.s.	105,3	93,80	105,3
12	b.s.	b.s.	b.s.	b.s.	b.s.	b.s.
13	169,1	102,3	b.s.	127,3	107,0	86,50
14	183,1	b.s.	155,8	156,0	189,8	183,0
15	b.s.	144,5	169,6	154,2	149,3	140,8
16	103,1	b.s.	71,80	129,8	112,7	137,4

Table III
Tensile strength of the samples. Six specimens from each sample.

A first glance at the data shows that the strength measurements of each sample spreads over a large dispersion of values. This is partly due to the intrinsic characteristics of the material and the production procedure, and partly due to the small size of the specimens employed, extremely sensitive to inhomogeneities in fibre and porosity distributions. Apart from the substantial dispersion of the results, some of the specimens broke at the beginning of the tests obtaining a "missing value" from them. They are marked as "b.s." (broken specimen) in table III. For the computing calculations they have been substituted by the row media (a value must compulsory be introduced for each specimen). All the specimens from sample number 12 broke in the machining process or when fixing into the testing grips. The reason for this occurrence is the deficient quality of the composite produced. For technical reasons a value of 60 MPa was assumed for the computing of the data.

A clear decreasing in strength is observed from the "inner specimens" (c and f), to the "outer specimens" (a and d) in most of the samples, although not large enough in value to be considered relevant. Similarly, the strength of the "lower specimens" (c, d, and f) is for most samples slightly higher than the strength of the "upper specimens" (a, b, and c).

A chronological study of the results reveals the no existence of systematic experimental errors (the cloud of points with no alignment tendency in figure 2 shows it. According to the selected models the data must fit into a normal distribution, and the variance must be constant or its variability model should be defined (6). The large differences in the results from each sample required a variance analysis (we selected Quantile or QQ-Plot) and subsequently a variance model, defined using multiple regression analysis (7), which results in Equation 1:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{e}{5} \quad (1)$$

$$(6,494304 - 0,640124 T_m + 0,552703 T_p + 0,66032 T_m Pr)$$

Figure 2
Systematic errors chart
(Tensile strength versus Number of experiments)

Figure 3
Variance model analysis
(Chi² versus QQ)

Figure 3 shows the model defined. Variances are employed as weights, omitting three and higher level interactions and assuming a 99,5% confidence interval. The equation defined according to these parameters (equation 2) is:

$$Y = 128,571697 - 20,132993 T_m + 7,381962 T_p - 8,30284 T_u + 8,185476 P_r - 7,787738 V_f T_m - 5,540952 V_f P_r + 7,411127 T_m P_r \quad (2)$$

Y = Stimated Tensile strength

The significance of the process factors (or variables) has been studied using the F statistic, where a 0.995% confidence interval is assumed. The analysis according to Anova gives an adjustment coefficient, R^2 , of the defined model to the experimental data of 0,73; which considering the large dispersion of the experimental data is acceptable. The residuals plot (difference between the calculated response and the measured response) showed that no specification errors were produced in the model, and their normal probability plot yields a normal population of the data, as supposed.

Equation 2 shows that all the variables have significant contribution to the process, as well as the interaction $T_m P_r$. This interaction can be confused with $T_p T_u$, but the technical knowledge of the process allows the choice between both. The processing parameters can now be optimised according to both equations. Initially the levels of the factors are set to minimise the variance in equation 1,

$T_m=+1 / T_p=+1 / P_r=-1$, and secondly to maximise the response in equation 2, $T_u= -1$. Due to the interactions between variables, the final set of the levels required a Response Surface Plot (figure 4).

Figure 4

Surface plot of the tensile strength versus Vf and Pr

Optimum values are obtained when:

$V_f = -1$ (10%) and $P_r = +1$ (50 MPa). Therefore, the process variables for the production of an optimum composite should fit the following values:

$T_m = +1$ (750°)

$T_p = +1$ (700°)

$T_u = -1$ (250°)

$V_f = -1$ (10%)

$P_r = +1$ (50 MPa)

The observation of the fracture surfaces shows the great difference between the specimens produced in suitable and unsuitable conditions. Figures 5 and 6 are obtained from fracture surfaces of specimens type 5 and 12 respectively. In them the good fibre-matrix bond and interface of the composites type 5 confront the large porosity due to deficient infiltration, and the lack of adhesion of samples type 12.

Figure 5 (x 1000)
Fracture surface of specimen type 5

Figure 6 (x 175)
Fracture surface of specimen type 12

4. CONCLUSIONS

1- The production of A356 aluminium alloy composites reinforced with Alumina short fibres by the squeeze casting process has been optimised according to an experimental design where the processing variables and their study interval are the fibre volume fraction (10-20%), the mould-die temperature (250-350°), the temperature of the metal (700-750°), the preform temperature (500-700°), and the infiltration pressure (10-50 MPa). The equation ruling the process in these conditions, for the production of optimum strength composites, is:

$$\text{Stimulated Tensile Strength} = 128,571697 - 20,132993 T_m + 7,381962 T_p - 8,30284 T_u + 8,185476 P_r - 7,787738 V_f \cdot T_m - 5,540952 V_f \cdot P_r + 7,411127 T_m \cdot P_r$$

2- The processing parameters for production of optimum composites according to the strength criteria and the selected variables intervals are:

Fibre volume fraction:	10%	Preform Temperature:	700°
Mould-die temperature:	250°	Infiltration Pressure:	50 MPa
Temperature of the metal:	750°		

3- Some extra experiments are required to check the validity of the defined equation, and further optimise the process.

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References

1. Terry, B., Jones, G., *Metal Matrix Composites. Current developments and future trends in industrial research and applications.*, Elsevier Advanced Technology Pub., England 1990, pp. 71-101.
2. Clyne, T.W., Mason, J.F., *Metallurgical Transactions A*, Vol. 18A, pp 1519-1530, August 1987.
3. Fukunaga, H., Goda, K., *Bulletin of JSME*, Vol. 27, No. 228, pp 1245-1250, June 1984.
4. Juran, J.M., Gyra F.M., *Juran's Quality Handbook. 4th. Edition*, Mc Graw Hill Pub., New York 1990, pp 26/14 - 26/16.
5. Cooper, B.E., *The extension of Yates' 2n algorithm to any complete factorial experiment*, *Technometrics*, Vol. 10, pp 575-577, 1968.
6. Polo, C., Pepió M., *Planificación de experiencias. Vol.2.* Univ. Politécnica de Catalunya Pub., Barcelona 1990.
7. Draper, N.R., Smith, H. Jr., *Applied Regression Analysis 2nd. Ed.*, Jhon Wyley and Sons, New York 1981.